

**A Note on the Flavanoid and other
Constituents of *Phyllanthus* Genus**

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PHYLLANTHUS niruri (Euphorbiaceae) possesses medicinal properties¹. A number of alkaloids, terpenoids, lignans, flavanoids and steroids have been reported earlier². No phytochemical work appears to have been done on the stem part of *P. niruri* and *P. urinaria*.

The air-dried stem of *P. niruri* was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°) and methanol. The concentrated extract was treated with water, and the aqueous filtrate extracted with ethyl acetate. The ethyl acetate extract on chromatography over cellulose gave a light yellow solid, m.p. 190°, C₂₇H₃₀O₁₆, which was characterised as quercetin-3-*O*-β-D-glucopyranosyl (1→4)-α-L-rhamnopyranoside. The aqueous filtrate on chromatography over cellulose afforded a yellow solid, m.p. 276–78°, C₁₅H₁₆O₆, which was identified (m.m.p., co-pc, uv, ir, pmr) as 3,5,7,4'-tetrahydroxyflavone.

P. urinaria (whole plant) was extracted with petroleum ether and chromatographed over silica gel column. The petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluate gave lupeol and α-amyrin. The chloroform-ethyl

acetate (3 : 1) eluate gave an aliphatic alcohol, m.p. 77°, C₃₄H₇₀O, which was identified from its spectral data as 32-methyl-1-tritriacontanol³.

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